

THEORETICAL PREREQUISITES FOR THE LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC CLASSIFICATION OF OIKONYMS

Chorakulova D.Z.

Lecturer at the Department of Russian Linguistics, Faculty of Philology, Bukhara State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12579170>

Abstract. *Oikonyms, as well as other linguistic units, are a full-fledged part of the language system, and that everything is organized within this system, it is necessary to note the effectiveness and prospects of such research, namely the lexico-semantic taxonomy of oikonyms. Lexico-semantic analysis of oikonyms, as well as similar analysis of appellatives, involves the study of semantic features of etymons, that is, those elements that are part of these units.*

Keywords: *oikonyms, lexico-semantic, toponyms, proper name, linguistics, ethnonyms, linguistic analysis, onym.*

The term lexico-semantic analysis involves the study of the vocabulary of a language, that is, a set of words and their semantics.

The meaning as an element of the "content plan" of a word does not exist in isolation, it is in diverse and multidirectional relationships and relationships with other meanings of the same word (if it is polysemous) and with the meanings of other words. In general, the semantic layer (level) The language is not a disorderly set of meanings, but their ordered system, the elements of which are in a relationship of interconnection and interdependence. The systemic organization of vocabulary is manifested in the presence of word combinations characterized by a certain community of meanings. Such word combinations are called lexico-semantic paradigms, and the semantic relations between the members of the paradigm are called paradigmatic relations [1].

One of the first who drew attention to the study of the series of words combined into separate microsystems based on the same associative-psychological concepts was A. A. Potebnya, who gave, however, from the position of subjective idealism, a well-founded analysis of individual dictionary groups from the point of view of etymology and further semantic development in the language of their constituent components constantly relying on facts from the history of the language [2].

In this regard, in his monograph "On the problem of semantic typology" B. Y. Gorodetsky suggests the allocation of levels in terms of language content, i.e. semantic levels. At the same time, the morpho-semantic level is distinguished, represented by the values of all morphemes distinguished in a given language, and the lexico-semantic level, represented by the values of all lexical units included in the lexicon of a given language [3].

Both linguistic and extralinguistic factors are involved in the processes of generating and understanding linguistic expressions in the natural conditions of human activity (in the context of our study, in the processes of naming or nominating settlements). A. A. Potebnya distinguishes the immediate and further meaning of any word, i.e. distinguishes "two types of information in the semantics of linguistic expression: linguistic (immediate meaning) and extralinguistic (further meaning)." [4].

Adhering to the opinion of N. K. Frolov says that the systematization of vocabulary "can be attributed to an independent field of research, where the object of attention is dictionary groups,

layers, rows, types in their diachrony and synchrony, combined on the basis of common origin, attitude to reality, sphere of functioning or word formation" [5], we come to the conclusion that that onomastic vocabulary, as well as appellative, should be systematized, and given the fact that oikonymic units are categorical units and their connection with the objects of reality can be clearly traced, their distribution by thematic headings is an important aspect.

The leading among the meanings of the word, according to N. K. Frolov, are "direct nominative meanings of the word, which are directed directly at objects and phenomena; the nominative meaning of the word reflects the public understanding of denotations, the meaning of the word is based on the concept, i.e. the thought of the subject, highlighting the common and most essential features in it." [6]. Referring to the researcher's opinion that "the verbal sign, being a two-pronged entity, reflects the interpenetrable opposition represented by the plane of expression, that is, the material shell or lexeme, and the plane of content - sememe, i.e., the meaning of the word or the minimum unit of semantic content" [7], it should be noted that the oikonym, being an otapellative sign, it also displays the opposition "lexeme – sememe", which is clearly presented in the empirical part of this dissertation research. A variant of the sememe, the semantic multiplier of the elementary meaning, is the seme or the smallest unit of the verbal sign, and the system of semes in its entirety forms a single semantic structure of the word – the semanth, i.e. the material part, the material (lexical) basis of the verbal sign" [8].

F. P. Filin hypothesizes about "the vocabulary of a language as a system of different lexico-semantic groups (rows, categories) of words" [9]. Based on the hypothesis of language as a system, it should be noted that a language sign cannot function outside the framework of this system. The system's reaction to the slightest changes in the language sign is inevitable. Accordingly, the diachrony of a sign, i.e. a word that is an integral part of a group, can only be taken into account when considering all segments of this group.

N. K. Frolov believes that "the procedure for distributing the components of a system, groups, consists in ordering and limiting words by sequencing their division into components (type-subtype), which are characterized by a gradual convergence (inclusion, intersection, concentration) of differential semantic features. In each specific classification of paradigms of different levels, one has to deal, firstly, with the logical-objective grouping of words, based on the identification of the relations of the objects of reality themselves, the ratio of classes of objects of reality, and, secondly, with generic-specific arrangements of lexical blocks based on semantic connections and linguistic forms." [5].

Based on the opinion of scientists that "the meaning of each significant word is based on the concept, i.e. the thought about the subject, highlighting the common and most essential features in it, and that the lexical meaning of a word is determined by the correlation of the word with the corresponding concept and the place of the word in the lexical system of the language, it reflects the historical connection between the sound of the word and the display of the object or phenomenon that occurs in our consciousness" [10], it is possible to say that oikonymic units, being an integral part of the lexical composition of a language, can also basically have an idea about a certain object, can generate certain associative concepts. The question of the presence of a lexical meaning in an onym has already been defined above, but it is necessary to note the specificity of the meaning of the onym, which indicates not a class of objects, but an individual object. Here it is necessary to emphasize once again the fact that all oikonyms are categorical units, and in order to identify the meaning of their constituent elements, it is necessary to resort to a

diachronic method of identifying the etymons underlying them for further classification based on lexico-semantic and structural features. Indeed, according to V. V. Vinogradov, "the word for the most part contains indications of adjacent rows of words and meanings" [11], and A. A. Potebnya, paying attention to the study of word series, argued that they "combine into separate microsystems based on associative psychological representations" [11]. K. B. Selezneva believes that "a proper name is characterized by a higher semantic abstraction".

A. I. Ufimtseva rightly notes that "thematic dictionary groups are based not on lexical and semantic connections, but on the classification of the objects of reality themselves, and the differentiation of lexemes by semantic features implies the grouping of words, firstly, depending on the thematic proximity of the concepts they designate, and, secondly, depending on semantic relations (compatibility, incompatibility, binary positions), which words enter into with each other and based on the position that, that the most objective linguistic criterion for distinguishing lexico-semantic groups is the presence of free semantic linear connections between words and their lexical meanings". Therefore, it can be argued that according to the same criteria, there is also a differentiation of economic etymons, which are revealed during the etymologization of these units. The main unit of etymological research is the etymon, which in the explanatory dictionary of S. I. Ozhegov is defined as "the restored original form and meaning of the original word or in general the linguistic unit from which the word of this language originated."

According to A. A. Beletsky, the components of etymological research should be attribution (attribution to a particular language), localization, periodization and connection of the onomasticon with appellatives, taking into account the structural and variable features of names. Y. A. Karpenko sees the prospects of etymological research in a systematic approach combining phonetic-comparative, word-formation and semantic criteria.

In the works of such toponymists as A. P. Dulzon, O. N. Trubachev, A.V. Superanskaya, A. K. Matveev, A. Y. Karpenko, N. Dilbaryan, N. Poghosyan, there is a special gradation of toponyms according to lexical and semantic headings. All toponymic material fits within the framework of seven to twelve lexical and semantic groups, limited in some cases to three or four or expanding to thirty or more groups and categories.

The variation in the number of groups and subgroups in total depends on the condensation of differential features of geographical objects or, conversely, on the granularity, which undoubtedly depends on the tasks and goals set for the study.

Lexico-semantic analysis of oikonyms, as well as similar analysis of appellatives, involves the study of semantic features of etymons, i.e. those elements that are part of these units. The identification of the etymon makes it possible for the researcher to form a clear idea of what the original lexical meaning of the onym (in our case, the oikonym) was, i.e. almost all proper names originated from certain appellatives. This method allows you to identify the origin of the oikonym, its original meaning and follow all its changes and evolution.

REFERENCES

1. Tuilieva, Lola. "Lexical aspect of the seme "burn." *CENTER FOR SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS (buxdu.uz)* 35.35 (2023).
2. Shadursky I. V. Thematic study of vocabulary // *The methodology of studying vocabulary.* Minsk: Belarus. u-tet, 1975, pp. 48-52.

3. Gorodetsky B. Y. On the problem of semantic typology. M.: publishing house of Moscow. unita, 1969, 564 p.
4. Potebnya A. A. From notes of Russian grammar. M.: State educational and pedagogical publishing house of the Ministry of Education of the RSFSR, 1956, 536 p.
5. Frolov N. K. Toponymy and ethnonymy // Selected works on linguistics. Vol. 2, Tyumen: Publishing house of the Tyumen University, 2005, 517 p.
6. Choraqulova, Dilnora. "THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE STUDY OF TOPONYMS." *Занкиевские чтения* (2023): 183-186.
7. Shermukhammedova, N. A. "TEXTS OF PROFESSIONAL ORIENTATION AS SOURCES OF ENRICHING SPEECH WITH TERMINOLOGICAL VOCABULARY." *World Science* 5 (38) (2020): 446-448.
8. Choraqulova, D. "OIKONYM AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC STUDY." *Science and innovation* 2.C10 (2023): 51-54.
9. Filin F. P. On lexico-semantic groups of words // *Yezikovedski issledovaniya v chest na akad. St. Mladenov*. Sofia: 1957, 624 p.
10. Levkovskaya K. A. Theory of the word M.: 1962, Kosovsky B.I., Types of word meanings // *Methods of studying vocabulary* (edited by E.A. Suprun). Minsk: 1975, 213 p.
11. Vinogradov V. V. The main types of lexical meanings of the word // *Questions of Linguistics*, 1953, N 5, pp. 7-27.
12. Potebnya A. A. From notes on Russian grammar. vol. 1-2 // [general ed., preface. and the introduction by V. I. Borkovsky]. Academy of Sciences of the USSR, Department of Literature and Language, Moscow: State Educational and Pedagogical Publishing House of the Ministry of Education of the RSFSR, 1958, 535 p.